

ISic0582

Dedication to the emperor Augustus by the municipium

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object

block

Editor

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2019-03-08 - Jonathan Prag edited the file based upon the edition prepared for Prag and Tigano 2017

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

First recorded by Antonio Agustín c.1559 (Prestianni Giallombardo 1993b), and then by Gualtherus (1624), who described it as being in the wall beside the main door of the church of S. Maria dei Palazzi

Coordinates

37.996429, 14.261916

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

no description is preserved

Dimensions

Height unknown cm

Width unknown cm

Depth unknown cm

Layout

no description is preserved

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

no description is preserved

Letter heights:

Lines 1-4: unknown mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: unknown mm

Text

1. Imp(eratori) · Caesarei ·
2. Divi · f(ilio) ·
3. Augusto · p(ontifici) · m(aximi)[.]
4. municipium

Apparatus

Text after Prestianni Giallombardo 1993

Gualtherus 1624: P.O.; Mommsen P.P

Translation (en)

The municipium (set this up) for Imperator Caesar Augustus, son of the divine

(Julius), Pontifex Maximus

Commentary

The text was first (and best) recorded by Antonio Agustín c.1559 (Matritensis 5781 f.22 no.3), and as Prestianni Giallombardo (1993b: 531) has made clear, he recorded the letters P.M. at the end of line 3. Gualtherus instead marked the letter(s) after the P as unclear, and in his edition of 1624 proposed reading O after the P, which Mommsen in CIL in turn emended to a P, to give P(ater) P(atriciae) (i.e. 'father of the fatherland', an honorific title of Augustus from 2 BC). P.M. is entirely possible however, and Augustus held the office of pontifex maximus (chief priest of the Roman state) from 12 BC onwards, which in turn provides a terminus post quem for this text, which should date therefore between 12 BC and AD 14. A parallel text is known from Haluntium (San Marco d'Alunzio), in CIL 10, no.7463 = ISic0587 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0587>]. This is one of several texts from Sicily erected simply in the name of the municipium (compare CIL 10, no.7463= ISic0587 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0587>] and 7464= ISic0588 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0588>] from Haluntium; AE 1945 no.64= ISic0622 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0622>] from Segesta), and the formulation is unusual, with occasional south Italian examples (Prag 2008: 78 nn.80-82), most likely reflecting Greek traditions of erecting honours, e.g., in the name of the polis (this possibility is made more likely by the example in Greek from Haluntium (IG 14, no.367 = ISic1190 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic1190>]), honours set up by τὸ μουνικίπιον τῶν Ἀλοντίνων). The text provides important evidence, alongside the Augustan coinage from Halaesa, that the town had the status of a Latin municipium by the later Augustan period.

Agustín and Gualtherus both note the use of distinctive hollow triangular interpuncts in the text (just once in Agustín, repeatedly in Gualtherus). Interpuncts of this precise form are also found in the dedication by M. Aimilios Rhodon (ISic0770 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic0770>]), which probably belongs in the second half of the first century BC and is therefore nearly contemporary. Solid triangular interpuncts are found in several of the first-century AD texts such as ISic3576 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3576>], ISic3577 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3577>], and ISic3575 [<http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk/inscription/ISic3575>]

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G. GUALTHERI

DEPERDITÆ. ET. QUÆ. OB. ABSENTIAM
dominorum, aut alia obstacula aspici non potuerit

In ad. Gersfeldi. terra abilita

294

SEMPRONIO
7. L. PRIMONI
ANNORVM. XVIII

In vineis. Lucis. apud Ant. Marchesium.
colite oblectata

295

MAZIMOC
IACONOC
ET. N. Z

Maximus
Iulianus F.
annorum LX

In maiori templo

291 STHENII AEDES

Legit Alph. Zappata veterem inscriptionem
non anteaquam investigaret

295

CEPHALOEDIS

Ad portam Piscariam. Intra foveam

296

ΣΑΞΙΝΥΜΒΟΝ
ΚΡΑΦΑΤΕ ΚΑΙΡΕ

Saxinumbon
Craffate fovee

D. MARIA. DE. PALATIO. seu. DE. PALATI
Il. lapide à Thusa, opido Fran. Viotimilla Marchionis Hieracij

Secus portam magnam in pariete

297

[IMN. . TATONAZ POIKIA]
[IXIII. COYCAPANTOCKI]

298

IMP Δ CAESAREI Δ
DIVI Δ F Δ
AVGVSTO Δ PO..
MVNICIPIVM Δ

Prope gradus, quibus ad aram maiorem astra
dicitur in marmoreis. in hac parte

298

ΘΕΟΣ ΠΑΤΕΡ
ΔΑΜΟΣ ΤΩΝ ΑΝΑΙΤΙΝΩΝ
ΔΙΟΓΕΝΗΝ ΔΙΟΓΕΝΟΣ
ΑΝΙΠΡΟΝΑ
ΔΕΠΤΕΣΙΑΣ. ΕΝΙΕΝ

Dicitur amuletum
populi Nalshurum
Drogatum Diogenis F.
Lapideum
Inventum in castra